

Determinants of Strategy Implementation in the Mandera County

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Abstract

The main aim of the research is to establish the determinants of strategy Implementation practices of the Mandera County Government. The research was directed by The McKinsey 7-S Model. The target population included senior management staff, middle management staff, and lower management staff. Thus from the above, the target population is composed of 58 respondents. The research used the census sample technique; the data collection instrument that was used to collect data from the selected respondents will include the questionnaire. The data was organized, edited, analyzed and interpreted using descriptive statistics. The study used the computer programmer SPSS version 23 to analyze the data. The regression model is also used to analyze the data. The results were presented using frequency tables, percentages, charts and graphs. The research findings indicated that top management commitment and organizational culture influence the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County. The findings of the study also indicated that individual responsibilities on the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County. The study recommended that the study recommends that leadership needs to support the performance of the county government in order to enhance efficiency and improve performance and that management offers financial support to increase implementation of strategies which is crucial for improving performance. There is also a need for the management to be very keen on making strategic decisions necessary in improving the county government's performance. The financial budget should be allocated every year to implement various strategies that are necessary for the improvement of county government performance. There is also a need for the county government to adhere to the set out guidelines on strategy implementation necessary for the improvement of organization performance and the staff should work intensively together with the management to ensure that the staffs are motivated to realize the county governments' strategies for improved performance

Keywords: Strategy Implementation, Government, Top Management Commitment, Organizational Culture. Performance

1. Introduction

Firms in any sector are operating in an environment that is dependent on each other and therefore the strategy it adapts depending on the environment that it operates in. In order for firms to continue to remain as competitive in the ever changing, difficult and unprecedented business environment, effective implementation of the necessary strategy is therefore important. Firms in any sector may be forced to often change due to the open systems they operate in even as they constantly interrelate with their surroundings and therefore must be able to develop ways that can ensure that they remain competitive. Businesses and firms in any sector use strategy to define goals and aims and recognize essential courses of action and distribution of resources that are required to attain the organization's goals (Chebat, 2013).

Organization strategy outlines a long-term plan that presents a master plan on goals to be attained in the organization's mission (Norman and Gaither, 2014). Organization strategies are incorporated in the firms' business plan, which entails a plan for all the operational areas of the firm that is inclusive of production, operations, marketing, finance among others. Strategic goals present the significant results that need to be attained by the firms or the business over the next period of time. Erez and Kanfer (2015) state that an organization's strategies describe why the process exists/should exist in the firm, and why it should be driven in

a certain way. Strategic objectives are focused or are intended to address the crucial organization needs. Many times, the most crucial goal of an organization is to achieve specific goals or maintaining some consistency.

Globally, different strategic management approaches are developed, affecting the way various sectors are being managed. Hasalaka (2015) acknowledges that strategic management is focused on answering the reasons that lead some organizations to attain high levels of achievement while others fail. While the field of strategic management has developed rapidly, there should be an attempt to investigate the strategic management practices of a particular sector. It is therefore crucial for each organization to properly understand the strategic management practices that it should put in place and the way it affects its operations in a given industry.

The objective of every competitive strategy is to ensure that the organization attain continued competitive advantage. This goal is attained by implementing competitive strategy that is referred to basically by the planned benefit of differentiation or low cost leadership. The transitory type of various collective competitive merits over the dynamic conditions of environment in South Africa needs that organization in depth comprehends the competition process and the factors influencing each advantage so that the company aligns itself to changes in such underlying conditions (Christensen, 2015).

The implementation challenge for new companies entering the markets in Uganda generates from lack of capacity in handling wide social, cultural, political and business extents, which interrelate in complicate and totally changeable methods during the adaptation of the strategies (Ojwok, 2016). These may force changes in the staff or business roles, initiative extreme organizational restraints, and innovative relations designs with other actors in the industry (Brinkerhoff, 2012). And therefore, the execution difficulty in the realization of the proposed strategy in full realization of the opposing forces or resistance.

Effective strategies are crucial for the overall performance with most organizations in Kenya developing strategies that are geared towards improving their performance and ensuring that they are effective. Good and effective strategies are vital to any institution that is serious on its performance and profitability (Musyoka, 2015). Organizations both private and public need to develop good strategies that can ensure that they deliver quality service to the public who are its customers.

While organizations acknowledge that development of effective strategies are important, it is evident that plan execution is a crucial difficulty for many businesses nowadays (Eriksson, 2016). There are many (soft, hard and mixed) issues that may affect the implementation of any plan successfully, that vary from the individuals who converse or execute the plan to the structures or tools in place for control and co-ordination. It is therefore crucial to properly comprehend relevant factors and how significant they are in successful implementation of strategy. The Kenyan 47 county governments have invested heavily in development of strategy to improve service provision and overall performance at the county government. Top management commitment, organizational culture, effective communication and individual responsibilities are crucial strategy execution practices so as for organizations to achieve the desired outcome. The research was aimed at determining the effect of strategy execution practices on the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County.

Implementation of strategies is crucial in achieving the desired performance in both private and public organization. Zaribaf and Bayrami (2015) pointed out that without a viable strategy and effective implementation process; institutions are unable to meet their objectives and goals. Organizational culture, communication aspect, top management commitment and individual responsibilities are some of the factors that have been identified as crucial in the implementation of organization strategies. As much as this, these strategies are important for the organization performance, earlier study has told that many executions are unsuccessful (Nutt, 2013). The average success rate of strategy implementation ranges as noted by Raps (2015) is between

10% and 30%. Mandera County like most other counties in the republic, though have written down strategies have not evaluated the influence of the implementation of these strategies in achieving the required performance. Despite the existing studies in strategy implementation, there are no researches on the consequence of strategy implementation on performance of Kenyan county governments and therefore cannot form any basis of generalization. Top management commitment, organizational culture of effective communication and individual responsibilities are crucial strategy execution practices in order for organizations to attain the desired goal. The research targeted at determining the effect of strategy implementation processes on the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County.

Theoretical Orientation

The study was guided by The McKinsey 7-S Model, McKinsey and Company came up with a theory that has been referred to as 7-S's or the seven Elements of strategic fit. These 7-S's comprises: Strategy of Coherent group of activities carefully chosen as a course of achievement; structure (separation of responsibilities as indicated on the company's plan); systems- comprises processes and flows that indicates how a company carry's out its things; style- how executive conduct themselves; staff-people in the company; shared-values that incorporates the values pooled by all in the institution; and skills which are the abilities acquired by the company(Kaplan and Norton,2015).

The fundamental concept of the model is that for effective strategy implementation all seven of these variables need to coincide with one another. On the other hand, values sharing are the more significant aspects of the context given that they are the heart-and Soul themes on which companies concentrates to enhance performance of the county (Bhatti, 2011). The representation of the model in Figure 2.1 below depicts the interdependency of the factors and indicates how a change would have an effect on others. The model is important to the study since top management commitment, organizational culture, communication and individual responsibilities should be part and parcel of the organization so as to improve the performance of the Mandera county Integrated Development Plan.

Figure 2.1 The McKinsey 7s Model

Source: Bhatti (2011).

The strategy that the organization develops will determine how they are going to be implemented by the organization. The organization culture that includes the shared values as one of the 7s is a hard factor in strategy

implementation given that without the right culture the organization is not able to meet its strategic goals. The staff being one of the soft factors is critical in the implementation of the organization's strategy. The strategic leadership style that represents management commitment determines how the organization implements its strategies. Effective communication of what the strategy is and applying the right skills to communicate the required information will determine how the strategy implementation is done in the organization. On the other hand the organization structure that defines all the staff responsibilities is crucial in the implementation of the organization strategies. It defines what actions individuals in the organization are responsible for.

Empirical Review

Influence of Top Management Commitment on Strategy Implementation

In relative to strategy implementation and performance top executive takes part in vital responsibility in every main business decision. Therefore, the achievement of any serious choice developed by the firm is depends to large extent to the top executive support and commitment (Zagotta & Robinson 2012). On the other hand, the top executive needs to take a top responsibility by making available the most vital resources, founding companies extensive quality strategy that is successfully talked to all participants, creating a valued management organization and running the whole practice via close observing and assessment.

In regard to strategy implementation, the significance of the Top Management Commitment cannot be overemphasized. Different studies are in support of this purpose as highly stated in a study by Bigler (2011) that showed 90% of organization strategy formulation in the USA and Europe can be said not attain the desired outcome because of not being implemented on time. Though plan preparation is celebrated, unluckily strategy execution in most cases gets a short drift (Freedman, 2013). Hendry and Kiel (2014) on the responsibility of the board in organization plan: there is need for the organization that decides on a specific strategy to ensure that they give their best to see it through as advised by integrating agency and organizational control perspectives.

Another study by Cobbold and Lawrie (2011), involved 200 companies. The study that involved 80% of directors established that they possessed the right plans but only 14% were of the opinion that they were implementing them well. They were of the opinion that no uncertainty related to the result that only 33% stated attaining important strategic successes in spite of 97% of directors having a vision that is strategic. Robinson and Zagotta (2012), also indicated that a CEO of any firm to be considered successful as ,they must be aware that strategy gets one to the initial line but implementation is what gets one the finish line.

The top management support at every level of management is crucial for strategy implementation in every sector, a study by Egelhoff (2013) on how top executive enhances commitment of medium managers to innovation strategy implementation due to the support they give in healthcare organizations, while using a mixed-method serial design, studied 120 and questioned 16 mid managers executing an innovation envisioned to decrease health differences in 120 US health centers to assess if higher executives' help impact directly the mid executives' commitment, by assigning execution strategies and exercises, or by controlling the outcome of execution strategies and exercises on mid managers' commitment. The study established that that top management support has significance influences on commitment of mid managers' to innovation strategy execution.

Keramati, and Azadeh (2015) explored the impacts of top executive's commitment on fulfilling management knowledge based method in Academia, through a Case Study established that top management commitment can be considered successful at the time when a firms manager or division accepts their role for the successful strategy implementation. Semi organized interview method was used in statistics gathering with help of an

interview conductor. The study advised that manager need to be involved and add the expertise and special skill that that raised them to be organization president and one will not believe how much common sense will be experienced and how effective implementation process will be.

Yeh et al (2016) in another research on the execution of organization strategies by the top management in leading multi organization in Africa, recognized that top managers develop and enhance the attainment of the mission, vision and overall plans, develop standards that are needed for lengthy achievement and implement these through suitable activities and behaviors, and they personally engage in making sure that companies management system is established and executed.

Strategy implementation is a challenge to many organizations, but with clear top management commitment the company can achieve its goals and objectives. Kimani(2015) argued that association between strategy execution and leadership in Manufacturing Business through a cases study established that effective executive management provides the definition of the firms objectives, review the available information/results of processes, and help in decision making and take action based on the necessary reviews while attaining the necessary strategy goals.

Influence of Organizational Culture on Strategy Implementation

The organization culture needs to be in resonance with the new strategic changes for it to be implemented effectively. According to Aosa (2012), it is significant that the firm's culture is steady with the plan being executed given that in existence of inconsistency amid plan and culture, then there could a high organizational opposition to the proposed change and low morale that can therefore make it difficult for effective strategy implementation.

Organizational culture is the organization mutual conduct of individuals in an institution, its formation includes; organization norms, visions, values, language in working, symbols, beliefs and habits, systems and structures. It is also the design of such mutual characters and assumptions that are taught as a way of seeing, thinking and feeling to new institutional members (Hill and Jones 2014). In most cases organizational culture influences the manner in which staff and various groups relate among themselves, with customers, and with shareholders.

Hartnell (2013) commenting on leadership as the starting point of strategy referred to organizational culture as a group of mutual emotional expectations that effect the explanation and act in the organization by indicating suitable conduct for numerous circumstances. A firm may poses its own different philosophy, in bigger firms, due to different traits of the executive team there is a varied and sometimes contradictory philosophies that co-exist. Hartnell (2013) on the significance of organization culture on the performance of organization the research warned that the organizational culture can also have adverse and optimistic features on the organization strategic goals and objectives.

There is robust difficult to the strategy execution caused in making of an organization's culture, that is fully synchronized with execution strategy. Aosa (2012) on association between cultures and plan execution observed that the inconsistency between plan and culture may result to a great organizational opposition to change and de-moralization that may then frustrate the implementation of any strategy. Rajasekar (2013) pointed out that firms that possess good organization culture among their members, for example culture free of corruption and with high integrity may be often viewed to be more profitable than the firms that are associated with bad company culture.

Akbari, Salamzadeh, Daraei and Ahmadi (2012) researched the effect of institutional culture while executing strategies Oil companies in Nigeria, established a important correlation between organizational culture and plan execution. The findings indicated that all kinds of institutional cultures have important relations with execution process, but the degree of the cultures' effect may be not the same from the most optimistic such as clan culture to the least optimistic such as hierarchy culture.

Making surroundings that connects staffs to the firm's mission and that makes them feel contented. To reward success reinforces the significance of directing on strategy and vision. A study by Omari(2014) on the problems to plan execution in Medium Size Companies in Kenya, the research focused on five manufacturing companies in Kenya and through interviews the study collected information from the senior managers and their deputies. The study advised that there was need to come up with some innovative optimistic and adverse consequences in attaining or not attaining the strategy. On the other hand, the benefits may be small or big, as long as they help the staff prioritize strategy implementation above the daily activities.

The organizations performance of county government of Mandera will highly depend on the execution of the set out strategies. Top executive commitment, organizational cultures and the communication process and channels will highly affect the implementation of strategies that are crucial in attaining the set out performance goals in the county government. On the other hand individual responsibilities that defines what tasks one is expected to perform will definitely influence the strategy execution in the county government that are necessary in achieving the organization performance goals.

Material and Methods

the study used a case study research design given that it is appropriate for reviewing complex social phenomena in which practical characteristics in the circumstances include; numerous variables of attention; numerous sources of proof; theoretical propositions to guide the gathering and examination of data. Given that the research covered all 58 management staff Mandera county government the study employed a census sampling method where all the units under investigation are covered. The research instrument denote to the tools that were utilized for data gathering and how the research tools were developed. The data gathering tools that were used to collect data from sampled study participants included the questionnaires. To test the reliability of a questionnaire, the study applied Cronbach alpha method. This approach was suitable in yielding greater internal consistency. A reliability coefficient of 0.781 was attained and therefore the research instrument was considered reliable. According to Serem *et al* (2013), a correlation coefficient of 0.70 and above is sufficiently regarded having satisfactory dependability. Regression model was also used to analyze the data as follows.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \epsilon$$

Where: Y = Strategy Implementation in Mandera County

X1, X2, X3, and X4 = Independent Variables

X1= Top Management Commitment

X2= Organizational Culture

ϵ . = Error Term

β_0 = Constant

$\beta_1 \dots \beta_4$ = Regression co-efficient of four variables

Findings and Discussion

This section therefore shows consequences and deliberations of the research from the information gathered from the questionnaires; whereby the study sort opinions and views on the influence of determinants of strategy

Implementation in the Mandera County. The chapter was divided in two units that include univariate and multivariate analysis

Univariate analysis

The study registered a mean of 3.0769 and a SD of 1.18564. While the response indicated a great variation in the responses, the findings stresses the need top management commitment, that are in consistent with the findings of Hendry and Kiel (2014) that advised that there is need for the organization that decides on a specific strategy to ensure that they give their best support on the decisions made in order to see it through. The study also supports the findings by Egelhoff (2013) that top management support has significance influences on middle managers' commitment to innovation strategy implementation. The study registered a mean of 3.1154 and a SD of 1.14881, which was a great variation in response and stresses the significance of organization culture in strategy implementation and is in consistent with the findings of Hartnell (2013) that warned that the organizational culture may also have negative and positive aspects on the organization strategic goals and objectives. The response in this part registered a mean of 3.6346 and a SD of 1.04841. This supports the findings of a study by Kaplan and Norton (2012) that pointed out that growth in Asset base of an organization is an indication of improved performance.

The first specific objective of the study was to determine effects of top management commitment on the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County. The findings of the study show that top management commitment has a significance influence on the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County ($r=.845$, $P<0.000$). This suggests that the performance among at the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County can be enhanced if top management commitment aspects are improved. The second specific objective was to determine the significance influence of organizational culture on the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County. The findings of the study shows organizational culture has a significance influence on the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County ($r=.698$, $<.000$). This suggests that the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County can be improved if organizational culture can be improved.

Table 1 Univariate analysis

	Mean	Std	Performance	Top Management	Organizational Culture
Performance	3.635	1.138	1		
Organizational Culture	3.077	1.186	.845**	1	
Top management commitment	3.115	1.149	.698**	.774**	1

Multivariate analysis

The coefficient of determinant (R-squared) of .612 that presents a 61.2% of the total variation in the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County and can be explained by top management commitment and organizational culture in Mandera County Government.. On the other hand the Adjusted R Squared of 0.579 indicates these strategy implementation practices (top management commitment and organizational culture), in exclusion of constant variable, explains the changes in the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County by 51.5%. The remaining (48.5%) can be explained by the factors not included in the regression model under investigation. The Table 1 above that shows a regression output of the strategy implementation practices (top management commitment, and organizational culture) as valid ($F(4, 47)=18.516$, $P<0.000$). This means that the strategy implementation practices (top management commitment and organizational culture) factors can be used as predictors explaining the variation in the Determinants of strategy Implementation Practices On Strategy Implementation in the Mandera County. The $P<0.000$ which is less than the critical value of 0.05 leads us to

reject the null hypothesis and accepting the alternative hypothesis that the strategy implementation practices (top management commitment and organizational culture has a positive and significant influence on the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County.

Table 2 **Multivariate analysis**

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	0.211	0.403		0.523	0.603
Top management commitment	0.198	0.167	0.204	1.185	0.042
Organizational Culture	0.122	0.191	0.128	0.643	0.023
Model Summary					
R	0.782				
R Square	0.612				
Adjusted R Square	0.579				
ANOVA (F stat)	18.516				
ANOVA (F prob)	0.000				

The Table 2 shows a regression results that indicates that all the strategy implementation practices (top management commitment, organizational culture, communication and individual responsibilities) ($X_1: \beta_1 = .198, P < .042$) and ($X_2: \beta_2 = .122, P < .023$) and would have a significant influence on the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County. All the two strategy implementation practices when combined that have significance influence on the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County although individual Responsibility factors would have the most significance influence on the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County, followed Organizational Culture and then by top management commitment factors would have the least significance influence on the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County.

$$Y = 0.211 + .198X_1 + 0.122X_2 + e$$

This indicates that a unit increase of 0.198 in top management commitment, of 0.122 in organizational culture would influence a unit change in the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County if everything remains constant at 0.211.

Conclusion

When the study sought to establish the effects of top management commitment on the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County, the findings of the study indicated that the decision making process at either the departmental level or top management influence performance of Mandera County. The study indicated that the management is very keen in making strategic decisions necessary in improving the county government performance and that financial budget is allocated every year to implement various strategies that are necessary on the improvement of county government performance. Finally, the study indicated that leadership support to enhance efficiency and improve performance and that management offers financial support to increase implementation of strategies which is crucial on improving performance.

The study had sought to establish the effects of organizational culture on the strategy Implementation in the Mandera County, the findings of the study indicated that there is adherence of set out guidelines on strategy implementation necessary for the improvement of organization performance, the staff work together with the management and are motivated to realize its strategies for improved performance and that the county strategic

plan is aligned to the organization mission and expected performance targets. The findings of the study also indicated that management style adapted are effective in influencing strategy implementation necessary for enhanced organization performance or felt that the county has a well-defined existing behaviour that has facilitated efficiency and effectiveness by implanting the necessary strategies and that the organization has set out values among employees for the implementation of organization strategies geared towards improvement of service delivery.

Recommendation

The study recommends that leadership needs to support the performance of the county government in order to enhance efficiency and improve performance and that management should offer the necessary financial support to increase implementation of strategies which is crucial on improving performance. There is also need for the management to be very keen in making strategic decisions necessary in improving the county government performance. Enough financial budgets should be allocated every year to implement various strategies that are necessary on the improvement of county government performance. Increased involvement in decision making process at either the departmental level or top management should be encouraged to influence performance of Mandera County.

There is also need for the county government to adhere to the set out guidelines on strategy implementation necessary for the improvement of organization performance and the staff should work intensively together with the management to ensure that the staffs are motivated to realize the county governments' strategies for improved performance. The county government should align its strategic plan with the organization mission and expected performance targets.

The role of organization culture in any organization is critical to the running and success of the organization. In addition, the issue of performance is determined by organization culture. Making the employees and everyone feel as being part of the success of the organization is essential towards the achievement of the objectives of the organization as well as its mission and vision. Enabling room for wide consultation with subordinates on the running of the organization. In addition, creating an enabling environment where relations between the managers and their subordinates are enhanced is critical to the performance of county government since trust and respect would be nurtured in such a setting.

There is need for a study on the challenges of strategy implementation in the county government. The communication strategies applied by the county government in the implementation of county government strategy.

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